

Association for Clinical Genomic Science (ACGS) Best Practice Guidelines for Variant Classification in Rare Disease

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ABSTRACT

Accurate classification of genomic variants is essential for the diagnosis of rare diseases and informed clinical decision-making. The Association for Clinical Genomic Science (ACGS) has developed standardised best practice guidelines, aligning UK variant interpretation with frameworks from the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics (ACMG) and the Clinical Genome Resource (ClinGen). These updated guidelines incorporating both sequence and copy number variants, also include mitochondrial, non-coding, reduced penetrance and hypomorphic variants as well as recommendations from the ClinGen Sequence Variant Classification Working Group. They emphasise a multidisciplinary approach and the importance of phenotype specificity to enhance variant interpretation. Variants of uncertain significance (VUS) are sub-classified using a Bayesian points system and those with limited evidence for pathogenicity, where additional testing would not upgrade the classification, are not reported. These guidelines provide general recommendations and detailed specifications for each ACMG evidence code plus recommended report wording. Ongoing updates to these guidelines reinforce consistency in UK variant classification while addressing specific national considerations for genomic testing in the NHS, ensuring alignment with international standards.

INTRODUCTION

Approximately 7,000 rare diseases have been described affecting an estimated 1 in 17 of the UK population (~3.5 million individuals). Over 5000 rare diseases are caused by highly penetrant single nucleotide variants (SNV), small insertion/deletion (indel) variants (<50bp) or copy number variants (CNV) involving a single gene or region. A prompt and accurate molecular diagnosis can be crucial for optimal clinical care, including increasingly in targeting treatment(1). However, diagnosis of a rare genetic condition can be challenging and is contingent upon a robust understanding of the molecular aetiology of disease, appropriate phenotypic information and large datasets of genetic variation.

The ACGS Best Practice Guidelines for Variant Classification in Rare Disease were first developed in 2017 for supplementary use with the ACMG/AMP guidelines(2) to achieve accurate and consistent use within UK and Irish laboratories. These updated guidelines include examples and notes to guide practice and provide clarification based on experience and queries raised by ACGS members. The term “SNV guidelines” (incorporating all small variants including single nucleotide and small indels) will be used throughout to refer to the ACMG/AMP guidelines and previous ACGS variant guidelines.

Further development of the ACMG/AMP guidelines has been undertaken through the US ClinGen Sequence Variant Classification Working Group (<https://www.clinicalgenome.org/tools/clingen-variant-classification-guidance/>) and a major revision to ACMG v4.0 is in progress. Multiple disease/gene-specific variant curation expert panels (VCEPs) have generated guidelines for their area of expertise. In 2020, guidelines specific for the interpretation of copy number variants (CNVs) were updated and released by the ACMG in collaboration with ClinGen(3).

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR VARIANT CLASSIFICATION

These guidelines are primarily intended for general use in classifying highly penetrant variants with Mendelian inheritance patterns including postnatal, prenatal and pregnancy loss setting. Some guidance for reduced penetrance, risk alleles and hypomorphic variants is included. Disease-specific guidelines have been developed for disorders where different evidence thresholds are required, for example familial cancer predisposition and inherited cardiac conditions.

Recommendation 1: It is essential that Clinical Scientists use their scientific and professional judgement for variant classification

It is not possible to describe every possible scenario and weighting that should be applied for each evidence criterion. Many variants prioritised by a bioinformatic pipeline will not require formal classification. Clinical Scientists should use proportionate variant analysis(4) to prioritise those variants that require a full classification, then collate and critically appraise evidence for/against pathogenicity in the context of the individual case under consideration.

Recommendation 2: Use of specialist VCEP guidance should be assessed for suitability by the appropriate specialist service and utilised where appropriate

Where there are inconsistencies with UK practice, any adaptations required should be agreed with all testing centres, documented and uploaded to the members section of the ACGS website using the available template. For CanVIG assessed and modified VCEP guidelines see <https://www.cangene-canvaruk.org/gene-specific-recommendations>.

Recommendation 3: It is essential that clinical and scientific data are both incorporated in variant classification

Interpretation of a variant for use in clinical decision making requires comprehensive knowledge of the patient's phenotype, mode of inheritance for the disease gene/region, mutational mechanism (e.g. haploinsufficiency), protein structure/function and the genotype-phenotype

association(5). Therefore, collaborative working between clinicians and clinical scientists is key for high quality variant classification. Clinicians have a responsibility to provide an appropriate level of clinical information to enable scientific interpretation of the genomic variant data. When requesting genomic testing the clinical team should provide details on the likelihood that a particular clinical presentation is monogenic or any specific diagnoses being considered. Phenotype specificity is a key evidence criterion for variant interpretation and when testing is undertaken at an exome/genome scale for diagnosis of very rare disorders, a multi-disciplinary (MDT) approach is optimal, involving the referring clinician, clinical scientist and other appropriate healthcare professionals. The purpose of the genomic MDT discussion is to assess the gene variant(s) identified in the context of the patient's phenotype data and ascertain their contribution to the clinical presentation. The format of the MDT discussion is flexible and includes e-mail correspondence with the key question "Is this patient's clinical phenotype consistent with the genetic variant identified?". If so, what is the strength of the evidence to support the variant classification? For variants of uncertain significance, the clinical team may suggest further genetic or non-genetic tests/investigations that result in variant reclassification to "likely pathogenic" (or "likely benign"). It is also important to consider the possibility that variants in more than one gene are contributing to the patient's clinical presentation(6). Of note, in settings where little clinical/phenotypic information is available (e.g. in the context of prenatal testing or newborn screening) these criteria should not be applied unless/until phenotypic status has been confirmed.

The ACMG variant classification guidelines may also be applied in interpreting sequence data from individuals with common disease phenotypes where the purpose is to identify high penetrance genetic predisposition. Examples include familial breast cancer and inherited cardiac conditions. Phenotypic information is often used to select individuals for genetic testing but additional information to underpin a robust interpretation will often be lacking in the absence of a family history. Caution is needed since (benign) rare variants and common phenotypes may coincide, phenocopies are common and other genetic and environmental factors may influence penetrance. Different evidence thresholds may be required in these disorders and UK disease-specific guidelines have been developed for inherited cardiac conditions(7) and familial cancers (original publication(8) and updated versions: <https://www.cangene-canvaruk.org/canvig-uk>) including classification of reduced penetrance variants in high-penetrance genes(9).

Recommendation 4: Variant classification should be undertaken independently from previously published classifications

Evidence from other laboratories (e.g. from ClinVar/DECIPHER) can be requested and used, alongside data from the patient under investigation, to aid variant classification. The variant assessment should include data, including phenotypic details, from all individuals identified with

the specific variant to date. Data sources should be saved and stored as an audit trail for any future queries.

Recommendation 5: Both SNV and CNV guidelines should be used for classification of CNVs

The ACMG/ClinGen CNV guidelines were developed to be applied to any CNV, irrespective of size or technology used for detection. As a result, both the CNV guidelines and SNV guidelines address the interpretation of CNVs involving a single gene. It is acknowledged that for some CNVs, the use of the SNV guidelines are more applicable (**Table 1**).

The CNV guidelines, unlike the SNV guidelines, have standalone evidence for a (likely) pathogenic classification. Therefore, we recommend applying the CNV guidelines to:

- deletion or duplication of a whole gene curated as a haploinsufficient (HI)/loss-of-function (LOF)/triplosensitive (TS) gene
- deletion or duplication involving multiple contiguous genes contributing to phenotype

It is recommended that SNV guidelines (PVS1 decision tree) are followed for CNVs that partially overlap a gene (including multigenic CNVs where a breakpoint is within the only gene relevant to the phenotype), intragenic CNVs and whole gene deletions/duplications of genes that have not been (recently) curated. **Figure 1** has additional details for the application of the PVS1 decision tree for partial overlapping CNVs.

The CNV point-based scoring metric was primarily created for the evaluation of autosomal dominant genes/genomic regions of reasonable penetrance. They were not developed with the intent to be independently applied to X-linked genes/regions or those associated with incomplete penetrance and/or variable expressivity; however, many of the concepts are useful for the evaluation of these genes/regions. The scoring metrics were also not created for the evaluation of autosomal recessive genes, therefore, except for whole gene deletions, we recommend use of SNV guidelines for CNVs affecting autosomal recessive genes.

Table 1: Example CNVs and which guidelines to use

Copy number variant	Recommended Guidelines & Criteria
Involving a single HI¹ gene or gene where LOF² is mechanism of disease	
Deletion with both breakpoints within the gene (involving coding exon/s)	SNV: Use ACGS PVS1 decision tree

Whole gene deletion (including both 5' + 3'UTRs)	CNV: Use 2A if gene is curated/established HI/LOF; otherwise use SNV (PVS1 decision tree)
Partial overlapping deletion: 5'UTR + coding exon/s	SNV: Use PVS1
Partial overlapping deletion: only 5'UTR, including well-established core promotor + transcription start site	SNV: Use PVS1 up to strong if evidence loss of region is disease-causing; upgrade to PVS1 if functional studies confirm LOF
Partial overlapping deletion: only 5'UTR, core promotor + transcription start site not included or not well-established	SNV: PVS1 not applicable
Partial overlapping deletion: only 3'UTR	SNV: PVS1 not applicable; consider up to PVS1 if functional evidence loss of region is disease-causing
Partial overlapping deletion: whole 3'UTR + last exon	SNV: Use PVS1_moderate; upgrade up to PVS1 if evidence loss of region is disease-causing
Partial overlapping deletion: whole 3'UTR + last exon + additional exon/s, NMD expected	SNV: Use PVS1
Duplication with both breakpoints within the gene (involving coding exon/s)	SNV: Use ACGS PVS1 decision tree
Duplication with one breakpoint within the gene	SNV: PVS1 not applicable if proven in tandem, direct orientation; if proved <u>not</u> in tandem, direct orientation consider up to PVS1, depending on predicted impact

Involving a single TS³ gene

Whole gene duplication (including both 5' + 3'UTRs)	CNV: Use 2A if gene is curated/established TS; otherwise use SNV (PVS1 decision tree)
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Multigenic CNV

Deletion involving multiple contiguous genes	CNV
Duplication involving multiple contiguous genes	CNV

Deletion involving multiple contiguous genes where only one OMIM morbid/causative gene fully explains phenotype

CNV: Use 2A if gene is curated/established HI/LOF; otherwise use **SNV** (PVS1 decision tree)

¹Haploinsufficient gene (loss of one copy of the gene results in a phenotype). ²Loss of function. ³Triplosensitive gene (gain of a copy of the gene results in a phenotype).

Small sequence variants

Supplementary Table S1 describes additional information to assist with the application of the ACMG guidelines. These must be used in conjunction with the detailed guidance published by Richards *et al*, and additional ClinGen recommendations. **Figure 1** is included as a useful supplement for the application of PVS1 in multiple scenarios.

Recommendation 6: Use of Bayesian-derived evidence points is recommended

The ACMG guidelines have been transformed into a quantitative Bayesian framework(10). We recommend use of Bayesian-derived evidence points(11) for pathogenicity or benignity to combine evidence and reach a classification (**Figure 2**). Except for BA1 or BS1 stand-alone codes, a minimum of two criteria are required to classify a variant as (likely) benign or (likely) pathogenic; therefore, variants with only one piece of evidence are classified as a VUS pending a second corroborating piece of evidence. Use of the Bayesian system allows more flexibility for combining criteria and allows multiple new combinations to be used in addition to those specified in (2). For variants where there is conflicting evidence, both in support and against pathogenicity, we recommend combining the Bayesian probability(10) but emphasise that expert judgement is always required. For example, it is not appropriate to use “*rare in population studies*” (PM2) and classify a variant as VUS when all other evidence suggests that it is benign. Garrett *et al* (11) sets out how conflicting evidence can be used during variant classification and gives examples of permissible and non-permissible combinations of codes to avoid double-counting same/similar evidence in cancer susceptibility genes. This has been further developed into a grid for every possible combination of evidence codes (see <https://www.cangene-canvaruk.org/canvig-uk-guidance>). The principles of Bayes’ theorem apply to variant classification in that each item of evidence in support of or against pathogenicity should be used only once.

Copy number variants

Supplementary Table S2 contains details from the ACMG/ClinGen guidelines and additional information to be used in conjunction with the detailed guidance and tables published by Riggs *et al*(3).

The ACMG/ClinGen guidelines developed a semiquantitative point-based scoring metric for classification of copy number losses (deletions) and copy number gains (duplications)(3). These points do not align with the SNV Bayesian evidence point system(11). A useful online tool for scoring CNV evidence is available here: <https://cnvcalc.clinicalgenome.org/cnvcalc/>.

Recommendation 7: The default recommended points for CNVs should be applied for each piece of evidence in most situations

A range of points is provided for most scoring categories in the ACMG/ClinGen guidelines to allow flexibility to upgrade or downgrade a certain piece of evidence. Examples of when to default from the recommended score are in **Supplementary Table S2**. If a decision is made to upgrade or downgrade points within the suggested range for a particular piece of evidence, the points allocated, should be static: (+/-) 0.15, 0.30, 0.45/0.60, 0.90/1.00 (these roughly equate to the SNV guidelines strengths of supporting, moderate, strong and very strong). For example, if the default recommended points for a piece of evidence is 0.30 and the range is 0 to 0.45, when downgrading apply 0.15 and when upgrading 0.45. When the default score of evidence is either 0.10 or 0.15 and a range exists, the points score should not be up or downgraded.

Recommendation 8: Classification of mitochondrial genome variants should use ACGS Best Practice Guidelines for the Molecular Diagnosis of Mitochondrial Disease

The evaluation of pathogenicity of mtDNA variants differs substantially from those detected in the nuclear genome, with additional considerations regarding levels of mtDNA variant heteroplasmy, the tissue being tested, mtDNA haplogroup and reliable variant frequency resources. Laboratories unfamiliar with mtDNA analysis should seek support from specialist mitochondrial centres in more challenging cases and utilise published guidelines (<https://www.acgs.uk.com/media/11935/bpg-for-the-molecular-diagnosis-of-mitochondrial-disease-ratified-november-2020.pdf>)(12, 13).

Recommendation 9: Classification of non-coding variants should use recommended published guidelines

Guidelines to aid classification of non-coding SNV variants are available(14). The discovery of recurrent pathogenic variants in the non-coding small nuclear RNA (snRNA) genes *RNU4-2*, *RNU2-2*, *RNU5A-1*, *RNU5B-1* and others associated with neurodevelopmental disorders demonstrates the clinical utility of WGS(15-19). However, proportionate variant analysis(4) is required to ensure that only non-coding variants with a high prior probability of pathogenicity are investigated.

Pathogenic variants in the 5'UTR are most commonly due to: (i) introduction of an upstream start codon creating an upstream open reading frame (uORF) (uAUG gained) (ii) change in existing uORF (iii) alteration of classical or primary Kozak context (iv) splicing (v) change in translational efficiency (vi) change in secondary structure(20). Pathogenic variants in the 3'UTR are most commonly due to: (i) altered miRNA binding (ii) impact on polyadenylation signal (iii) impact on mRNA stability(21). The UTRannotator tool is available in DECIPHER to predict impact on uORF(22).

Similarly, CNVs involving non-coding RNA genes that have been reported in association with specific disorders (e.g. MIR17HG) can be classified using the SNV guidelines if this fits the disease mechanism and is the only causative gene implicated.

Recommendation 10: The approach to classifying variants in genes associated with multiple disorders or different inheritance patterns depends on disease mechanism

To classify variants in semidominant genes where both autosomal dominant and autosomal recessive disease caused by the same molecular mechanism, with varying severity of the phenotype (e.g. *LDLR*, *F11*, *VWF*) the evidence for pathogenicity can be aggregated for both monoallelic and biallelic cases.

Where variants in a gene are associated with distinct disorders based on different modes of inheritance with the same mechanism of pathogenicity (e.g. *ATM* gene associated with loss-of-function monoallelic hereditary cancer predisposition and biallelic ataxia-telangiectasia), evidence for pathogenicity can be aggregated across both conditions to reach the same final classification.

For variants in a gene associated with distinct disorders due to differing mechanisms of pathogenicity (e.g. *RET* gene associated with gain-of-function multiple endocrine neoplasia type 2 and loss-of-function Hirschsprung disease) variant classifications for each disorder should be distinct. Therefore, likely benign or benign classification should only be attributed to the variant if it is not associated with either disorder. If a variant is (likely) pathogenic for one distinct disorder, it should be classified as VUS (not (likely) benign) for the other to avoid misinterpretation.

For additional guidance see: https://clinicalgenome.org/site/assets/files/9380/clingen_guidance_for_classifying_variants_in_genes_associated_with_multiple_disorders_v1.pdf.

REPORTING RECOMMENDATIONS

The evidence and hence variant classification are dependent upon knowledge at the time of the

assessment, and it is important that service users understand that new information or guidelines may change the classification.

Recommendation 11: If testing does not identify (likely) disease-causing variant(s), the report should clearly state that the result does not exclude a genetic diagnosis.

Genetic analysis may involve classification of multiple variants, but the genomic laboratory report and any appendices should only describe those that are relevant to the clinical question i.e. VUS with high probability of being causative, likely pathogenic or pathogenic variants. Results included within the genomic laboratory report will form part of the patient's clinical record and should be unambiguous to a non-specialist.

Example NHS reports are available on the members area of the ACGS website <https://www.acgs.uk.com/> and <https://www.cangene-canvaruk.org/canvig-uk-report-templates>.

Recommendation 12: Variants should be reported using ISCN or HGVS nomenclature where possible

Reports must include the human reference genome build when genomic nomenclature is used, and the clinically appropriate transcript and version number (e.g. MANE select and/or MANE clinical plus) where cDNA nomenclature is used. To reduce ambiguity for non-specialists, a clear description of the variant in words should be included in the main body of the report e.g. pathogenic missense variant, likely pathogenic copy number loss involving exons 2-6 in NM_000251.3, pathogenic copy number gain of 113 OMIM morbid genes etc. For intragenic CNVs, it is crucial that the description should be unambiguous, ideally including the systematic numbering of impacted exons in a specific named reference sequence and ideally, clear HGVS/ISCN describing the variant (where this is known) or genomic coordinates of the CNV including limitations of the assay used (e.g. MLPA). Terms such as (copy number) loss or deletion and (copy number) gain or duplication should be used to describe the genomic imbalance. The term 'duplication' should only be used when the underlying mechanism of the abnormality is known. The genotype of the variant should be included in its description and where applicable reports should define the position of variants (e.g. interstitial, terminal, tandem, inverted).

Recommendation 13: The variant classification should be included within the results section of the laboratory report

The report should include clear information regarding the gene-disease association and mode of inheritance. We recommend that the evidence criteria/type and strengths/points used for variant classification is included in an appendix to the report. This may be omitted for recurrent

pathogenic variants with a large body of evidence in the literature or ClinVar. When using the SNV guidelines, evidence points may also be added where useful, particularly if a variant is at the borderline of clinical actionability between VUS and likely pathogenic (see example Hereditary cancer reports <https://www.cangene-canvaruk.org/canvig-uk-report-templates>). Variants classified as likely benign or benign should not be reported.

Recommendation 14: Standardised report wording should be used

In **Supplementary Table A** we summarise recommendations for reporting genomic variants. This table describes which variants to include in the laboratory report, text that should be used within the result summary box and explanatory notes. Additional specific notes for recessive disorders are provided in **Supplementary Table B**.

Recommendation 15: For recurrent CNVs we recommend that those with a haploinsufficiency/triplosensitivity score of 3 (sufficient evidence) equates to a Pathogenic classification, a score of 2 (emerging evidence) equates to Likely Pathogenic, and a score of 1 (little evidence) equates to VUS

Many recurrent dosage sensitive regions and genes have been curated by the ClinGen Dosage Sensitivity curation group (<https://www.clinicalgenome.org/>). We do not recommend the reporting of recurrent regions/genes that have been assigned a score of 1 (VUS). Those that have a score of “40” (dosage sensitivity unlikely) equates to a Benign classification.

The classification of a CNV should be consistent irrespective of the clinical setting, however the decision on whether to report certain CNVs in a prenatal or pregnancy loss versus postnatal setting may vary depending on the clinical presentation.

Reporting of Variants of Uncertain Significance (VUS)

Richards *et al*(2) state that a variant of uncertain significance (VUS) should not be used in clinical decision making. The reporting of VUS can be challenging and the consequences of a misdiagnosis due to misunderstanding the significance of a reported VUS may have wider implications beyond the proband. It is essential to use clinical judgement and consider discussion in an MDT.

Recommendation 16: VUS can be classified into three sub-groups

With the caveat that current variant classifications are semi-quantitative, the likelihood of a VUS being pathogenic ranges from 10-90% and (2) noted that “*some laboratories may choose to sub-classify VUSs, particularly for internal use*”.

Figure 2 illustrates sub-classification into three VUS groups, using posterior probabilities and a

Bayesian points scale to convey the different levels of uncertainty. Whilst laboratories and clinicians may find it helpful to use VUS sub-classifications, these should not be included in the laboratory report.

Recommendation 17: VUS should generally only be considered for reporting where there is a high level of supporting evidence and additional evidence might be obtained to allow re-classification as (likely) pathogenic

This might include discussion with the referring clinician to determine whether parental samples might be available to demonstrate a *de novo* variant and confirm parental relationships; if there are sufficient affected relatives (informative meiosis) available to demonstrate co-segregation; e.g. whether neuroimaging, muscle biopsy or biochemical testing could provide phenotype specificity evidence; whether trial of a treatment specific for the genetic aetiology (e.g. biotin in a patient with biallelic *BTH* variants) or mRNA analysis to confirm aberrant splicing. If additional evidence could allow re-classification of the variant as (likely) pathogenic, the initial report should clearly state the further action recommended to potentially upgrade the variant classification (see **Supplementary Table A**).

The emphasis is on additional testing to obtain evidence in support of pathogenicity. In some cases, the new information will re-classify the VUS as likely benign, but routine practice should not include additional testing to prove that a variant with little supporting evidence is benign.

Recommendation 18: There may be exceptional circumstances in which an MDT discussion concludes that there is clinical utility in reporting a VUS where the potential for reclassification is unclear

In some circumstances it may be impossible to obtain sufficient evidence at the time of reporting to reach a variant classification of (likely) pathogenic. Where all the available clinical, gene-level and variant-level evidence supports the likely diagnosis, MDT discussion is essential. One scenario is a rare autosomal recessive disease with a specific phenotype and one (likely) pathogenic variant plus a VUS with a high level of supporting evidence (see **Supplementary Table B**).

The prior probability of pathogenicity for a VUS is particularly important. For example, strong family history, the specific gene/region (or biological pathway) is indicated by the referring clinician, or the clinical presentation suggests a very high likelihood of the genetic disorder.

In most clinical settings and for most genes/regions, VUS with a low level of supportive evidence are unlikely to be disease-causing and should only be reported in exceptional circumstances after MDT discussion. These are often novel variants (absent from literature and databases) and frequently are either missense variants in genes with missense constraint or where *in silico*

tools predict a deleterious effect on protein function. This level of evidence should be considered circumstantial in the absence of a high level of phenotypic specificity. Another example is novel contiguous gene CNVs that do not contain any established disease-associated genes linked to the patient's phenotype or have the required number of genes to apply 3C but often contain predicted dosage sensitive genes. In the absence of literature or database evidence, determining if these CNVs have arisen *de novo* or are segregating with a phenotype within a family may not result in enough additional points to change the classification of these variants, especially when detected in individuals with non-specific phenotypes. It is recommended that these variants and phenotypes are added to DECIPHER <https://www.deciphergenomics.org/> to help with the future interpretation of these regions.

There are some specific exceptional circumstances where a prior decision may be made by the laboratory and expert clinical team to report certain VUS in specific genes. Examples include where a well-established specific pharmacological therapy is recommended for a genetic disorder, and a treatment trial may be considered for certain VUS e.g. low dose sulphonylurea therapy is recommended for monogenic diabetes patients with (likely) pathogenic *HNF1A* or *HNF4A* variants(23).

Recommendation 19: There are specific situations where reporting a VUS would not be considered appropriate

- (i) Variants previously reported in the published literature and databases as pathogenic/likely pathogenic for which subsequent scientific evidence has re-classified the variant as likely benign or benign. Examples include NM_020975.6(*RET*):c.2372A>T (p.Tyr791Phe)(24) and NM_007294.4(*BRCA1*):c.594-2A>C(25). There is no clinical utility in reporting these historical false positive results.
- (ii) Variant type that does not fit with the established disease mechanism, for example protein truncating variants predicted to result in nonsense-mediated decay in a gene where the known disease mechanism is gain of function.
- (iii) Heterozygous VUS in a gene only associated with an autosomal recessive disease, where a second candidate variant has not been detected.
- (iv) CNV with a negative points score.

Specific VUS reporting considerations related to WGS and WES

An evidence-based framework for assessing gene-disease associations has been developed by the ClinGen group(5). Variants identified within a “*gene of uncertain significance*” should always be classified as VUS(2). Such variants should only be included in the genomic laboratory report if there is robust evidence for the gene-disease association and publication is pending.

An updated report should be issued after publication to include the reference.

The advent of genome sequencing has not only identified many new disease genes not previously associated with human disease, but also identified novel phenotypes linked to known disease genes, thereby expanding the phenotypic spectrum. For clinical diagnostic testing, the focus must be on known gene-disease associations. For example, if a novel variant is identified in a gene associated with a particular set of phenotypic features but the patient's clinical presentation fits with only a single/subset of non-specific features of the disorders or is out-with the phenotypic spectrum associated with the disease gene, one might hypothesise that the restricted clinical presentation is a consequence of the missense variant having variable penetrance or expressivity or that the patient represents an extension of the currently established disease spectrum. In the absence of other phenotypically matched individuals with similar variants confirmed by functional studies, a case series establishing a new phenotype association with the disease gene or additional robust evidence, such variants should not be reported.

Recommendation 20: Reporting of carrier status in an autosomal recessive gene as a default approach is not recommended

For single gene or targeted testing where the prior probability of a particular autosomal recessive disorder is high, the finding of a single monoallelic variant involving a gene associated with the autosomal recessive disorder would be reported as “at least a carrier and this result increases the likelihood of a diagnosis of disorder X”. An example would be an individual with a positive sweat test undergoing testing for common *CFTR* variants. This reporting rationale is based on (a) the prior probability from the phenotype and (b) the incomplete nature of the test i.e. testing only the most common pathogenic *CFTR* variants.

When testing large gene panels, WES/WGS or a chromosomal microarray, if a single monoallelic (likely) pathogenic variant involving a gene associated with an autosomal recessive disorder is found, it means that either (a) incidental carrier status has been revealed or (b) a second variant has been inherited *in trans* but has not been detected. If the individual's phenotype is not compatible with the disorder or (biallelic) variant(s) explaining the phenotype have been identified in another gene, then this is likely to be an incidental finding.

Every individual is likely to be a carrier for multiple rare diseases and reporting those variants in the context of a test to investigate the cause of the patient's rare disorder has greater potential to mislead than to appropriately inform. Further guidance on managing incidental findings within the NHS is available (<https://bsgm.org.uk/media/12577/bsgm-managing-incidental-findings-guidance.pdf>).

In the situation that we find a single monoallelic (likely) pathogenic variant in a gene associated with an autosomal recessive disorder and the patient's phenotype is compatible with this

disorder, then the decision to report will depend upon the phenotypic specificity, size of the gene panel, known clinical sensitivity of the test and whether a second variant might be detected by additional analysis of the genomic data or another diagnostic testing method. Single heterozygous variants in autosomal recessive genes should not be reported unless there is additional testing that the laboratory would recommend that is likely to help confirm the diagnosis in the proband.

Reporting of reduced penetrance variants, risk alleles or hypomorphic variants

Where lower penetrance genes or genetic variants are included in a gene panel test, any low penetrance pathogenic variant(s) identified are unlikely to account for the majority of the phenotype/risk and this should be clearly articulated. Reduced penetrance, risk alleles and hypomorphic variants should only be reported in relevant clinical contexts. These variants, especially those with limited evidence, can be difficult to classify using current guidelines and should be clearly described in reports using recommended terminology(26). See **Supplementary Table C** for report recommendations for these variants.

Recommendation 21: Standardised terminology for reporting of Reduced Penetrance Variants should be used e.g. “(likely) pathogenic, reduced penetrance”; “(likely) pathogenic with low penetrance and variable expressivity”

Reduced penetrance variants cause disease with the same inheritance pattern as fully penetrant variants, however, may show later age-of-onset, different spectrum of clinical features and/or be asymptomatic. Many recurrent microduplication/microdeletion CNVs are associated with incomplete penetrance and variable expressivity. Some CNV regions are more highly penetrant than others(27, 28).

Example: The NM_175914.5(*HNF4A*):c.340C>T (p.Arg114Trp) likely pathogenic variant has high frequency in population studies, lack of co-segregation in some pedigrees and inconsistent functional studies. A case-control study confirmed it is a pathogenic variant causing a distinct clinical subtype of *HNF4A* MODY with reduced penetrance, reduced sensitivity to sulfonylurea treatment and no effect on birth weight(29).

Recommendation 22: Risk (susceptibility) alleles may be reported in appropriate clinical contexts using standardised terminology “established” / “likely” / “uncertain” risk allele.

Well established SNV variants that confer a small increased risk of disease (odds ratio (OR) >2) may be reported, in appropriate clinical contexts as indicated on the NHS National Test Directory e.g. Gilbert syndrome and hereditary haemochromatosis. The ClinGen low penetrance / risk allele working group framework(26) to determine their classification is based on the strength of association studies (very strong/strong/limited evidence) depending on the number of cases

plus controls ± functional studies. These variants should not be reported in the absence of an appropriate phenotype as the absolute risk of disease remains low.

Examples of established risk alleles with very strong association studies (meta-analysis) include: NM_000410.4(*HFE*):c.845G>A (p.Cys282Tyr) common variant associated with Hereditary Haemochromatosis; 75–85% of homozygotes do not develop *HFE*-related HH(30); NM_001379610.1(*SPINK1*):c.101A>G (p.Asn34Ser) common variant (~1% of NFE alleles on gnomAD) in linkage disequilibrium with promoter variant is associated with increased risk of chronic pancreatitis with OR 6.82 for heterozygotes and OR 97.74 for homozygotes(31).

Recommendation 23: Standardised terminology for reporting of Hypomorphic variants should be used

Hypomorphic variants show a partial loss of gene function that may only result in a clinical phenotype when inherited with another deleterious variant and may show a different inheritance pattern (usually recessive) or phenotype to full or reduced penetrance variants. Such variants should only be reported in appropriate clinical contexts. We recommend the use of “established” hypomorphic variant and “likely” hypomorphic variant.

Example: Polycystic kidney disease due to heterozygous *PKD1* pathogenic variants is usually an adult onset, autosomal dominant disorder (ADPKD). However, rare, severe, very early onset (VEO) PKD is caused by biallelic *PKD1* variants, including at least one hypomorphic variant. Biallelic *PKD1* pathogenic variants are embryonic lethal. NM_001009944.3(*PKD1*):c.9829C>T (p.Arg3277Cys) is the most widely reported and characterised hypomorphic *PKD1* variant with sufficient evidence, including functional studies, to classify as an “established” hypomorphic variant in VEO-PKD. However, it is frequent in gnomAD and does not cause cysts in isolation in heterozygotes; therefore, in a heterozygous state in classic adult-onset ADPKD patients it should not be reported. Homozygotes for this variant do develop adult-onset PKD including end stage renal disease therefore it is appropriate to report homozygotes(32). A second common likely hypomorphic variant NM_001009944.3(*PKD1*):c.9499A>T (p.Ile3167Phe) causing VEO-PKD when *in trans* with another causative variant has been reported in at least 10 individuals from 7 families with VEO-PKD and has a high gnomAD v4.1 frequency including several homozygotes. This variant should be reported as a “likely” hypomorphic variant in the context of VEO-PKD only if *in trans* with a second causative variant(33).

Care is required to ensure known hypomorphic variants are not automatically filtered out (e.g. due to gnomAD frequency) for relevant referrals.

Recommendation 24: Reclassification of variants that affect clinical actionability should be shared and agreed with all NHS laboratories involved prior to the variant being reported

Variant data and relevant associated information must be stored within the laboratory in a way

that allows reclassification if required.

Reclassification of a variant across categories that fundamentally changes the clinical relevance – i.e. where variants cross the VUS-likely pathogenic clinical actionability threshold in either direction – should be shared with relevant health care professionals promptly. Care should be taken to amend existing reports for all relevant patients with the clinically significant reclassification (including patients analysed by different laboratories, where known). The new classification evidence should be placed in ClinVar so it is widely available. An email alert flagging clinically relevant changes in variant classification in cancer susceptibility genes is available to all registered users of <https://canvaruk.org/>.

Variant classification guidelines are evolving rapidly and changes to guidance may result in reclassification of variants in the absence of new evidence for/against pathogenicity. In cases where the reclassification changes from borderline likely pathogenic to borderline VUS, caution should be exercised as this classification may be subject to further change as guidelines evolve. Recommendations for laboratory reporting, including report wording and clinical management in such cases for cancer susceptibility genes is available(34) and may also be applicable for other rare disease cases.

Recommendation 25: Variant classification data should be shared in public databases

It is the professional responsibility of the Clinical Genomic community to ensure data is shared responsibly for improved patient care, using the ClinVar, CanVar-UK, and DECIPHER databases as appropriate.

Conclusion

These ACGS guidelines provide a comprehensive, evidence-based framework to support consistent and clinically robust variant classification across rare disease genomic testing. They integrate updated ACMG/ClinGen recommendations and clarify points raised by ACGS members to promote high-quality, standardised variant classification, particularly for variants of uncertain clinical significance. These guidelines are primarily aimed at NHS laboratories but may be helpful for other clinical services working within a public healthcare system. Ongoing refinement ensures alignment with emerging tools/data/evidence and international standards.

In memory of Dominic McMullan

We dedicate these guidelines to the late Dominic McMullan for his extraordinary contributions to this field and the wider practice of clinical genomic science over the past 35 years.

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